

Appendix A

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Figure 1. Photos of the studied biotopes in surroundings of the cordon Taratinsky: 1 – river sand banks; 2 – thickets of willows; 3 – glade in the floodplain deciduous forest; 4 – edge of the floodplain deciduous forest - west side; 5 – floodplain meadow; 6 – edge of the floodplain deciduous forest - east side; 7 – floodplain deciduous forest interiors; 8 – edge of the floodplain deciduous forest - north side.

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Figure 2. Photos of the studied biotopes in the surroundings of the Sosnovka village: 1 – open habitat; 2 – edge of a mixed forest; 3 – open habitat; 4 – open habitat; 5 – edge of a young pine forest; 6 – in the depth of a medium-aged birch forest.

<i>Rhizophagus parallelocollis</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)					2								
<i>Rhizophagus picipes</i> (G.-A. Olivier, 1790)										1			
Nitidulidae													
<i>Carpophilus hemipterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)									1			1	
<i>Carpophilus marginellus</i> Motschulsky, 1858												2	
<i>Cryptarcha strigata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	3	7	23	14	30	18	2	9	20	32	16	7	31
<i>Cryptarcha undata</i> (G.-A. Olivier, 1790)			2	10	4	35	1	3	45		9		35
<i>Cydramus luteus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)			4	4	9			1		1			1
<i>Eपुरaea guttata</i> (G.-A. Olivier, 1811)			1	1	2	4		1	2		2		5
<i>Eपुरaea</i> sp.	1	36	46	9	61	6	6	12	21	31	11	14	23
<i>Glischrochilus grandis</i> (Tournier, 1872)	24	14	72	7	12	9	5	35	10	50	8	7	12
<i>Glischrochilus hortensis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	14	10	13	15	14	10	5	60	6	64	17	45	35
<i>Glischrochilus quadriguttatus</i> (Fabricius, 1777)		5	87	26	42	3			8	7	16	1	11
<i>Glischrochilus quadripunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		4	3		8								
<i>Glischrochilus quadrisignatus</i> (Say, 1835)		1	1				4	3				3	
<i>Ipidia binotata</i> Reitter, 1875		1						1					
<i>Meligethes</i> sp.	1												
<i>Omosita discoidea</i> (Fabricius, 1775)					1								
<i>Omosita japonica</i> Reitter, 1874								1					
<i>Soronia grisea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	26	10	34	10	14	20	32	43	16	33	83	27	25
		9		4	2	5			6				2
Silvanidae													
<i>Psammoecus bipunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1792)												1	
Cucujidae													
<i>Cucujus haematodes</i> (Erichson, 1845)										1			
<i>Pediacus depressus</i> (Herbst, 1797)									1				1
Phalacridae													
<i>Phalacrus</i> sp.							1						
Latridiidae													
<i>Corticaria</i> sp.	1												
Coccinellidae													
<i>Chilocorus renipustulatus</i> (L.G. Scriba, 1791)						1				1			

<i>Anaspis thoracica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)					1								
Cerambycidae													
<i>Agapanthia villosoviridescens</i> (DeGeer, 1775)												1	
<i>Alosterna tabacicolor</i> (DeGeer, 1775)			1		1								
<i>Anoplodera sexguttata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)													1
<i>Aromia moschata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	18						1	1	7			2	1
<i>Leptura quadrifasciata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1	3							1				
<i>Leptura thoracica</i> Creutzer, 1799	1												
<i>Necydalis major</i> Linnaeus, 1758									1		1		1
<i>Purpuricenus kaehleri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)								1	4				
<i>Rhagium mordax</i> (DeGeer, 1775)	1	1	2	3	6	2	1		3	7		1	6
<i>Rhagium sycophanta</i> (Schrank, 1781)				1						1			
<i>Stenocorus meridianus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				1							1		
Orsodacnidae													
<i>Orsodacne cerasi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						5							1
Chrysomelidae													
<i>Altica</i> sp.	1												
<i>Cassida vittata</i> Villers, 1789	1												
<i>Crepidodera aurata</i> (Marsham, 1802)					5								
<i>Crepidodera fulvicornis</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	1												
<i>Crepidodera nitidula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)					1								
<i>Galerucella lineola</i> (Fabricius, 1781)												1	
<i>Galerucella pusilla</i> (Duftschmid, 1825)											1		
<i>Gonioctena linnaeana</i> (Schrank, 1781)	5												
<i>Lema cyanella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)												1	
<i>Lochmaea caprea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1							1				1	
Anthribidae													
<i>Gonotropis dorsalis</i> (Gyllenhal, 1813)											1		
<i>Tropideres albirostris</i> (Schaller, 1783)							1	3	1				
Curculionidae													
<i>Anisandrus dispar</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	47	23 5	13 8	74	16 5	24	5	58	79	10 6	43	37	45
<i>Anthonomus pomorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1	1										
<i>Anthonomus rubi</i> (Herbst, 1795)									1			1	
<i>Cleopomiarus distinctus</i> (Boheman, 1845)								1					
<i>Hypera conmaculata</i> (Herbst, 1795)							1						
<i>Mononychus punctumalbum</i> (Herbst, 1784)								1					
<i>Phyllobius oblongus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1				1							1
<i>Phyllobius pomaceus</i> Gyllenhal, 1834								1		2	1	2	

<i>Phyllobius pyri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1						6	1				2	2
<i>Polydrusus pterygomalis</i> Boheman, 1840			1										
<i>Sitona lineatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1												
<i>Tachyerges decoratus</i> (Germar, 1821)	1												
<i>Xyleborinus saxesenii</i> (Ratzeburg, 1837)				1				1		5			
Total of individuals	17	57	59	44	84	54	10	31	71	42	45	21	80
	8	3	2	6	4	1	5	1	7	1	8	8	7

Table B2. Species diversity and a total of Coleoptera individuals collected using beer traps in № 2

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6
Carabidae						
<i>Amara aenea</i> (DeGeer, 1774)			1			
<i>Amara tibialis</i> (Paykull, 1798)	1					
<i>Calathus melanocephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)					1	
Histeridae						
<i>Hypocaccus rugifrons</i> (Paykull, 1798)						2
<i>Margarinotus striola</i> (C.R. Sahlberg, 1819)						1
<i>Paromalus parallelepipedus</i> (Herbst, 1791)						1
Silphidae						
<i>Necrodes littoralis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)					1	
<i>Oiceoptoma thoracicum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1			1	7
Staphylinidae						
Staphylinidae sp.	5	1	3	1	3	42
<i>Lordithon lunulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)					1	
<i>Quedius dilatatus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)					1	1
Scarabaeidae						
<i>Cetonia aurata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	13	4	9	32	3	2
<i>Gnorimus variabilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)					1	
<i>Phyllopertha horticola</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1					
<i>Protaetia fieberi</i> (Kraatz, 1880)		3				
<i>Protaetia marmorata</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	1	3		3	1	4
<i>Protaetia cuprea volhyniensis</i> (Gory & Percheron, 1833)	9	5	11	7	1	
Scirtidae						
<i>Contacyphon variabilis</i> (Thunberg, 1787)						1
<i>Microcara testacea</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)		1				
Elateridae						
<i>Actenicerus sjaelandicus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1764)				1		
<i>Agriotes lineatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	1					
<i>Agrypnus murinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	5	1	12	6	1	
<i>Ampedus pomorum</i> (Herbst, 1784)						1
<i>Ampedus sanguinolentus</i> (Schrank, 1776)						3

<i>Melanotus castanipes</i> (Paykull, 1800)						9
<i>Prosternon tessellatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1	1		1		26
Cantharidae						
<i>Cantharis livida</i> Linnaeus, 1758		1				
<i>Cantharis nigricans</i> O.F. Müller, 1776			1			4
<i>Cantharis pellucida</i> Fabricius, 1792						1
Dermestidae						
<i>Globicornis emarginata</i> (Gyllenhal, 1808)		1				
<i>Trogoderma glabrum</i> (Herbst, 1783)		2	1		1	
Throscidae						
<i>Trixagus</i> sp.						4
Cleridae						
<i>Thanasimus formicarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
Melyridae						
<i>Cordylepherus viridis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)				1		
<i>Dasytes niger</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)		1				2
Monotomidae						
<i>Rhizophagus fenestralis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
Nitidulidae						
<i>Carpophilus hemipterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1			1	2	
<i>Cryptarcha strigata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	23	24	8	6	10	15
<i>Cychramus luteus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)						2
<i>Epuraea</i> sp.	6	40	14	31	19	74
<i>Glischrochilus grandis</i> (Tournier, 1872)	31	29	15	26	33	141
<i>Glischrochilus hortensis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	6	17	10	6	5	158
<i>Glischrochilus quadripunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1	2	1		1	3
<i>Glischrochilus quadrisignatus</i> (Say, 1835)	2			3		1
<i>Meligethes</i> sp.						1
<i>Soronia grisea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	42	30	9	26	31	34
<i>Soronia punctatissima</i> (Illiger, 1794)					1	
Coccinellidae						
<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> Linnaeus, 1758			2	2		
<i>Exochomus quadripustulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1			1	
<i>Hippodamia variegata</i> (Goeze, 1777)						1
<i>Hyperaspis campestris</i> (Herbst, 1783)						1
<i>Propylea quatuordecimpunctata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
<i>Subcoccinella vigintiquatuorpunctata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			1			
Mycetophagidae						
<i>Litargus connexus</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)						1
<i>Mycetophagus piceus</i> (Fabricius, 1777)						1
Tenebrionidae						

<i>Bolitophagus reticulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)		1				
<i>Lagria hirta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				1		
Anthicidae						
<i>Notoxus monoceros</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	1					
Scraptiidae						
<i>Anaspis frontalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
<i>Anaspis</i> sp.			1		1	
Cerambycidae						
<i>Aromia moschata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1	1	1		1
<i>Leptura quadrifasciata</i> Linnaeus, 1758		2			3	28
<i>Leptura thoracica</i> Creutzer, 1799		2		1	6	51
<i>Necydalis major</i> Linnaeus, 1758					1	
<i>Pachyta quadrimaculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				1		
<i>Purpuricenus globulicollis</i> Dejean, 1839					1	
<i>Rhagium mordax</i> (DeGeer, 1775)	3	1	1		4	29
<i>Rutpela maculata</i> (Poda von Neuhaus, 1761)						1
<i>Xylotrechus antilope</i> (Schoenherr, 1817)				1		
Chrysomelidae						
<i>Bromius obscurus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
Brentidae						
<i>Protapion interjectum</i> (Desbrochers des Loges, 1895)			1			
Curculionidae						
<i>Anisandrus dispar</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	3	15	7	8	5	86
<i>Dorytomus dorsalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1					
<i>Hylurgus ligniperda</i> (Fabricius, 1787)				1		
<i>Magdalis frontalis</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)		1				
<i>Miarus ajugae</i> (Herbst, 1795)	1					
<i>Phyllobius argentatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						1
<i>Phyllobius maculicornis</i> Germar, 1823			2	2		
<i>Phyllobius pyri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	9		8	11	1	
<i>Pissodes castaneus</i> (DeGeer, 1775)	2		6			1
<i>Strophosoma capitatum</i> (DeGeer, 1775)		1	4			1
<i>Xyleborinus saxesenii</i> (Ratzeburg, 1837)						1
Total of individuals	169	192	129	180	141	749